

Virtual Bronchoscopy – An emerging tool to diagnose ‘H’ type Tracheoesophageal Fistula (TEF)

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INTRODUCTION

Most of the pediatric surgical conditions or major congenital malformations are diagnosed on spot or with simple radiological imaging just like Tracheoesophageal Fistula (TEF), e.g., Inability to pass NG tube with coiling of NG tube on chest X-ray. But a few of them are still challenging to diagnose, just like ‘H’ type TEF because of delayed presentation as well as absent classical symptoms. (1) And even in today’s era where radiological accuracy has reached to a new level, this diagnosis is missed many times and only confirmed on table. Here we are reporting a case of ‘H’ type TEF, a 17 days old male child, whom we diagnosed on single attempt with virtual bronchoscopy.

CASE REPORT

A 22-day-old neonate presented to the Pediatric outdoors with complaints of cough and severe reflux post breastfeeding. She had been symptomatically treated for the same complaint at some private hospital for last 10 days but had persistent symptoms. Mother complained of coughing during feeding since last 20 days which was not associated with vomiting or abdominal distention. Patient’s antenatal history was uneventful with birth weight of 2.9 kg. There was no history of neonatal jaundice or any NICU admission at birth. Patient was referred to our hospital for non-resolution of symptoms. From above history and examination a communication between trachea and esophagus was suspected and CT and virtual bronchoscopy was performed which was suggestive of H-type trachea-esophageal fistula. Patient was planned for exploration and surgery was performed successfully, where the fistula was doubly ligated and transected with the cervical approach, Right side cervical approach was preferred as on CT the level of fistula was at T1-T2. Cervical excision was given. The fistula site was found exactly below the excision. On tracheal site prolene stay was taken and on esophageal side vicryl stay was taken. Fistula was divided, tracheal side closed with non absorbable suture (prolene 5-0). Local muscular flap was raised and placed

between two suture line to avoid further adhesion. Esophageal site was closed with vicryl 5-0 over 7 no infant feeding tube. A glove drain was placed and removed on POD 4.

Baby was kept on NG feed till POD 8 then contrast study was performed and continuity was confirmed. NG removed and breast feeding started on POD8. Patient was discharged on POD 8 on spoon feed and breast feed.

DISCUSSION

As compared to type C and type A TEF, gross type E or type H TEF is a rare anomaly, only accounting for 4-5% of all congenital oesophageal malformations.^{1,2}

Usually, diagnosis is missed in early neonatal period as there is absence of typical esophageal atresia. And before suspecting the diagnosis, these babies have had a history of hospitalization in view of aspiration pneumonia.^{7,8}

Even in today’s time, none of the tests used for diagnosis of H type TEF showed 100% sensitivity.^{9,10} Multiple attempts of investigations especially contrast study (e.g., Barium esophagogram, Gastrograffin esophagogram, Methylene Blue dye test) makes the babies’ lives more prone for complications.^{3,4,5,6}

Availability of neonatal bronchoscope or esophagoscope and expertise in performing these in neonates is still restricted to few centres. All these factors make this rare condition more challenging to diagnose. But nowadays, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a great tool and is becoming the replacing invasive counter option of it. Many a times in the past, chest CT was used for diagnosing H type TEF, but only succeeded in 50% of cases. 3D reconstruction of CT imaging and virtual bronchoscopy make this investigation more fruitful in neonatal period as we did in our case.^{11,12} An extra opening clearly visible in posterior wall of trachea and on over-imposed of two plane images along with virtual bronchoscopy show air filled fistula between oesophagus and trachea, which makes a confirmed diagnosis.

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A flow chart made by Sampat K and Losty P.D. in their meta-analysis study 2021 showed various diagnostic methods used as primary investigation for H type oesophageal atresia e.g., Contrast esophagogram (n=245), contrast plus esophagoscopy (n=1), tracheo-bronchoscopy alone (n=6), tracheo-bronchoscopy with esophagoscopy (n=14),

esophagoscopy alone (n=2), and high-resolution CT (n=6). (1)

Majority of patients underwent contrast study at many centres, but virtual bronchoscopy, being easily available at most of the tertiary centres, can easily replace these contrast studies and make the diagnosis more accurate.

CONCLUSION

In the era of artificial intelligence (AI), virtual endoscopy is an emerging tool to diagnose H type TEF. We just need a strong clinical suspicion, an experienced surgeon, and a dedicated NICU team to take care of these babies after making the correct diagnosis.

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